

INTRODUCING STARTUP TECHNOLOGIES TO MODERN RESTAURANTS AND THEIR ENHANCEMENT IN USING

Suvonov Ziyobidin Shaminovich¹

assistant

Abdukholikova Sarvinoz Ravshanjon qizi²

student

¹Samarkand institute of economics and service

²Samarkand institute of economics and service

(Samarkand, Republic of Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6727254>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

startup, restaurant,
modern technology,
innovation, foreign
experiences.

ABSTRACT

Startups are business models that are newly created and expandable and are one of the most widely used methods of business in the globalization process. Food Service also enhances its performance by using various techniques as one of the most advanced social sciences. One of the ways we can take as an example are startups with innovative technologies. It is given some points about international experiences of modern restaurants on using innovational startup projects in this article. Various activities are being carried out to establish the link between innovative technologies and business in all spheres of our country.

Today, the concept of startups and attention to modern business are highly developed. In particular, we can emphasize that, our country pays special attention to the creative entrepreneurship of young people. Various activities are being carried out to establish the link between innovative technologies and business in all spheres of our country. Startups are business models that are newly created and expandable and are one of the most widely used methods of business in the globalization process. Food Service also enhances its performance by using various techniques as one of the most advanced social sciences. One of the ways we can take as an example are startups with innovative technologies.

Worldwide, there are scientific and practical works are carrying on startups. Here are some of the key features of world-class startups:

Involved funds - 14%

Business model - 24%

Ideas - 28%

Team - 32%

Efficient use of time - 42%

As for the economic indicators of the startups in the catering sector, access to the food supply services has soared to 51%, and the European food supply services have reached over 300 million dollars in a year. In 2013, the \$ 1.38 billion investment was made for the world-famous startups that directed to food services, and 37.4% revenue has been taken from them.

McDonald is one of the premier startup projects of its time and now, which has a special place in the dining service and has made a great turn.

It can be said following startups that offered by many companies to restaurants.

CULINARY AGENTS. The "Culinary Agents", launched in 2012, connect the job seekers to the kitchen and dining rooms they need. Today, the business has about half a million users that support nearly 20,000 hospitality businesses across the country. Like "LinkedIn for Restaurant", this business also deals with a number of jobs (including job seekers), including full-time, part-time and seasonal jobs. In the "gigs" section of the beta release, qualified workers can also hire a temporary short-term job vacancy. Even when it is not the season for restaurants, "culinary agents" work well for employers and job seekers who have been discharged from restaurants throughout the country.

KITCHEN CUT. In 2011, veterinarian of the restaurant industry John Wood joined with Engineering Team to make a consistent search for the cost of cooking and making it. Kitchen Cut, along with 2,000 partner restaurants, helps you to determine which foods are most profitable, which is most demanded and whose price is most preferable. The kitchen also has the ability to detect calories and control allergens to inform employees or better explain to the audience. Despite being out of London, Kitchen Cut has its own reputation outside of Britain. Since its founding, it has retained its smaller size (20 workers) and lower incomes (self-sufficiency).

PLATE IQ. While the other companies in this list deal with the data analysis at home, Plate IQ uses data to solve a number of home-based operations. The platform will probably automate the most exciting part of the restaurant, billing, and It helps you to deal with supply chain management throughout your mission. Plate IQ can collect information about components in specific areas that can be reported to their

partner restaurants while consuming too much food and helping sellers sell their prices information can also be provided. This information can also be used for pricing foodstuffs. Launched in 2014, Plate IQ works with 5,000 restaurants.

SALIDO The use of many individual systems can lead to a loss of information that can lead to loss of revenue during the generalization process. Salido is a solution for restaurants offered within the same system of sales, labor management, advanced reporting, product and payment systems. This is a daily dining and kitchen display system, including daily operations of the restaurant. Salido has transaction around \$ 500 million in 150 locations across San Francisco from London. Restaurant customers include Eleven Madison Park, ABC Kitchen, Shuko, Eatly and others. Leading restaurants should create products for the team of the food industry, who have great experience in investment strategies and technical operations in the restaurant industry.

TRIPLESEAT. Delphi, a hotel management software manager, is encoded in the Microsoft DOS operating system in 1985. Its new owner, Amadeus, has been rebuilt on the widely used Internet-platform Salesforce. This is a good product. But there is room for competition. Six years ago, formerly, the Tripleseat program was built using the latest software for Internet-programming languages and the first line of code. Potential shareholders use their white-colored form to get the invitation. Then, the Event Manager uses Tripleseat to create suggestions, event orders, contracts, and invoices. The program monitors call in a calendar and save all contacts and chat-based conversations together. Tripleseat connects 95 percent of its customers every

year, and this year it is expected to grow by 40 percent. Its search engines bring to corporate clients such as corporate events like Bizly and social networking sites like Facebook, as well as to restaurants.

In summary, any startup projects are based on many experiences, research and results. Startups such as Facebook, Microsoft, Apple, Xiaomi (RedMi), Alibaba group (AliExpress) did not come automatically. There is also such an axiom in the world that 99 out of every 100 startups fail. It means that if the industry is constantly working on the development of the industry, the goal will be achieved.

In the face of new methods and technologies in every aspect of modern business, the ability to get rid of

competition can be limited. Specifically, the above-mentioned technologies are among them. By constantly developing and improving competitiveness and bringing more productive technologies into the industry, the higher the chance of gaining higher profits. Additionally, creating new jobs through startups is an achievement of social and economic well-being. Taking into account that a lot of work is being done to create startups in our country, it is also possible to have a great deal of experience in introducing national brands through a thorough examination of international experience. Considering the startups as a key factor, we can create enormous economic opportunities in our country.

References:

1. "8 Food Startups That Will Change Your Life", [<https://spoonuniversity.com/lifestyle/8-food-startups-that-will-inspire-you-and-change-your-life>];
2. "Skift Table's Top Restaurant Tech Startups to Watch 2018" [<https://table.skift.com/2018/07/24/top-restaurant-startups/>];
3. "The Future of Food: the Best Start-Ups for Restaurants" [<https://www.finedininglovers.com/stories/restaurant-startups/>].